

Determining Wavenumber-Frequency Relationships for Cochlear Slice Models

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Abstract. Finite-element, cochlear slice models include detailed organ of Corti morphology and present an opportunity to uncover micromechanical processes within the cochlea. This detail comes at the expense of cochlear length, which prevents the development of a traveling wave, but one can be simulated using Floquet periodic boundary conditions. Since the traveling wave can be described by the real component of the wavenumber-frequency relationship (WFR) for a given place along the cochlear length, we explored methods to determine physiologically appropriate WFRs for cochlear slice models. Puria and Steele outlined an approach to compute the real part of the WFR using the local volume stiffness of the partition (Puria and Steele, *The Senses: A Comprehensive Reference – Mechano-Acoustical Transformations*, **3**, 165-202 (2008)). This value depended on the pressure difference across the partition and the corresponding traverse area change of the partition, which was obtained in our models using stationary studies. While this method approximated the wavenumber for regions below and near the best frequency, Shera and Altoe described a method that accounted for the transition between the two regions using an iterative approach based on the partition admittance (Shera and Altoe, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, **120**(41), e2305921120. (2023), calculated in this work from its stiffness. De La Rochefoucauld and Olson also described a method to obtain the real part of the WFR but instead used a complex impedance (de La Rochefoucauld and Olson, *Biophysical Journal*, **93**, 3434-3450 (2007)), which we calculated by dividing the local pressure difference across the partition with its velocity obtained in frequency domain studies. To test our methods, we created a slice model with a relatively simple geometry to match that of a previously described full-length model (Xia *et al.*, *TO THE EAR AND BACK AGAIN - ADVANCES IN AUDITORY BIOPHYSICS: Proceedings of the 13th Mechanics of Hearing Workshop*, **1965**(1), 030006-1 – 030006-7 (2018)). The WFR for a given place in this full-length model was obtained from the slope of the velocity-versus-place phase. By comparing the results between the WFR from the full-length model with the relatively simple geometry and the computed WFRs from the corresponding slice model, we aimed to evaluate the methods most useful for determining the WFR of slice models with more physiologically accurate organ of Corti features.

INTRODUCTION

One of the hallmarks of cochlear mechanics is the traveling wave first described by von Békésy [1]. Full-length cochlear models capture this property naturally by implementing a stiffness gradient along the cochlear partition in addition to fluid spaces that narrow from base to apex. However, these models become prohibitively computationally expensive with the addition of more detailed organ of Corti (OoC) anatomy such as thousands of outer and inner hair cells and supporting cells. One computational approach to better understand cochlear micromechanics is to incorporate OoC details but limit the longitudinal extent of the model. Such an approach was developed and outlined in Maftoon *et al.*, 2018 [2] and more recently explored in Tubelli *et al.*, 2022 [3] using a 20- μm thick slice of the gerbil cochlea with anatomy from approximately the 2.5 kHz region.

One issue that arises from reducing the length of the cochlea is that a traveling wave does not develop and must be simulated. To incorporate local wave-like mechanics, we imposed Floquet boundary conditions on the longitudinal faces of the slice model, which allowed for independent manipulation of the stimulus and geometric periodicity. Since the Floquet boundary condition required a wavenumber-frequency relationship (WFR) as input, we set out to

determine a method for calculating a physiologically appropriate WFR for a given cochlear slice model. We did so by comparing the full-length model described in Xia et al., 2018 [4] and a slice that was created by extruding the geometry at the 7 mm location (Fig. 1).

FIGURE 1. COMSOL Multiphysics finite-element gerbil cochlear models. (a) Full-length box model from [4] with two fluid spaces and a partition comprising of a basilar membrane split into arcuate and pectinate zones. (b) Slice model created from partitioning and extruding the 7 mm location geometry in *a*. The model was stimulated by transverse velocity in the ST and SV.

METHODS

Four methods were used to calculate the WFR across our models: one for the full-length model and three for the slice. The full-length model WFR was taken from the slope of the arcuate-pectinate junction velocity phase with respect to place, as was described in [5]. In our model, the phase slope was calculated from +/- 50 μm longitudinally about the place of interest (7 mm from the base).

Slice Method 1

For the slice, the first method to calculate the WFR used the volume stiffness of the slice as outlined in Puria and Steele, 2008 [6]. Here, the geometry of the slice model was reduced to the partition only (i.e. no fluid) and solved in a stationary study with a pressure load on the SV-facing surface. The volume stiffness of the slice was calculated by dividing the prescribed pressure by the transverse partition area change

$$S_{Vol} = \frac{p_{diff}}{\Delta A} . \quad (1)$$

The area change itself was calculated by integrating the total volume displacement of the ST-facing surface and dividing by the slice width (20 μm). This effectively reduced the problem to two dimensions, which aligned with the approximations described in [6] and produced the 2D WFR

$$k^2 = \frac{2\rho\omega^2}{AS_{Vol}} \frac{kH}{\tanh(kH)} \quad (2)$$

where k is wavenumber, ρ is density, ω is angular frequency, A is scala area, and H is scala height. For equal-side, square cross-section scalae, the wavenumber approximated to long and short-wave regions (Eq. 24 in [6])

$$k_{lw} = \sqrt{\frac{2\rho\omega^2}{S_{Vol}H^2}} \quad (3)$$

$$k_{sw} = \frac{2\rho\omega^2}{S_{Vol}H} . \quad (4)$$

Equations 3 and 4 come from the inviscid approximation. Incorporating fluid viscosity μ , a viscosity parameter γ was defined $\gamma = \frac{H^2 \rho}{\mu} \left(\frac{8S_{Vol}}{2\pi\rho} \right)^{1/2}$. Puria and Steele then extended the wavenumber for large γ to be

$$k_{\text{visc}} \approx \frac{2\rho\omega^2}{S_{Vol}H} \left(1 + (1-i) \frac{8\omega^{3/2}}{\pi(2\gamma)^{1/2}} \left(\frac{2\pi\rho}{8S_{Vol}} \right)^{3/4} \right). \quad (5)$$

Viscosity modifies the real part of the wavenumber and makes it complex with a negative imaginary part, but we are only concerned with the real component in this study to avoid constraining the transverse response magnitude.

Slice Method 2

The second slice method adapted this approach to account for the transition between the two regions and is based on work by Shera and Altoe, 2023 [7]. They defined the driving pressure p_{BM} over the scala-averaged pressure \bar{p} as

$$\frac{p_{\text{BM}}}{\bar{p}} = \frac{kH}{\tanh(kH)} = \alpha \quad (6)$$

such that

$$k^2 = -\alpha \frac{2i\omega\rho}{A} \frac{w_{\text{BM}}i\omega}{S} = -\alpha \bar{Z} Y_{\text{BM}}^{\text{passive}} = \alpha k_{\text{w}}^2 \quad (7)$$

where S is the partition stiffness (units of pressure over displacement), w_{BM} is the BM width, \bar{Z} is the fluid impedance, and $Y_{\text{BM}}^{\text{passive}}$ is the passive BM admittance. Notably, since k and α are mutually dependent, the wavenumber is solved via numerical iteration

$$k^2 = \sqrt{\alpha k_{\text{w}}^2 (1 + \beta)} \quad \cup \quad \alpha = \frac{kH}{\tanh(kH)} \quad (8)$$

with β as the amplification factor (set to 0 in this study as we are considering a passive model).

Slice Method 3

The third slice method used the complex, frequency-dependent impedance to compute the WFR and was outlined in de La Rochefoucauld and Olson, 2007 [8]. Here, the specific acoustic impedance of the OoC was calculated as the pressure difference between points 10 μm above and below the arcuate-pectinate junction of the BM divided by the average transverse velocity of the partition

$$Z_{\text{OoC}} = \frac{p_{\text{diff}}}{v_{\text{BM}}} \quad (9)$$

The 3D WFR was obtained by taking the positive, real root (solved for analytically) of the dispersion relation outlined by de Boer

$$k^3 + k^2 \left(\frac{1}{\varepsilon b_0 H} + i \frac{2\omega\rho}{Z_{\text{OoC}}(x)} \right) + i \frac{2\omega\rho}{b_0 H^2 Z_{\text{OoC}}(x)} = 0 \quad (10)$$

with ε the fractional width of the scala occupied by the BM and b_0 a dimensionless quantity determined from the fit between two equations in [8]. Since the complex impedance was calculated using velocity, the model was solved in the frequency domain. However, this required a WFR input. We proceeded iteratively and alternated between solving the finite-element slice model using a given WFR to obtain a frequency-dependent, complex impedance and calculating a new WFR from that impedance, which was then used to resolve the model.

RESULTS & CONCLUSIONS

The full-length box model magnitude and phase response for six frequencies are shown in Figure 2 along with the real component of the WFR calculated from the phase about the 7 mm place. The best frequency (BF) at this location was 1250 Hz. The WFR of the full-length box model showed linear growth in the low-frequency, long-wave region, and faster, quadratic growth after around 1000 Hz—slightly below the BF. The wavenumber continued increasing above 2000 Hz, but at a slower, more linear rate. While the phase did plateau for high frequencies, indicative of the fast wave response [8], those frequencies were more than three times above BF. This was higher than the range of our wavenumber calculations, so the wavenumber rate decrease was not due to the plateau itself or being near the plateau. Latter figures limit the wavenumber calculation to twice the BF.

FIGURE 2. Full-length box model longitudinal response and WFR. (a) Model arcuate-pectinate junction (APJ) transverse velocity magnitude as a function of longitudinal place for six frequencies of stimulation. Values are shown with respect to stapes longitudinal velocity. Vertical gray dashed lines show 7 mm \pm 50 μ m. (b) Model APJ velocity phase for the same six frequencies, shown in the legend. The best frequency (BF) was 1250 Hz, as shown in *a*. (c) Real component of the wavenumber calculated from the phase in *b*. Colored dots correspond to colored lines in *a* & *b* (e.g. green dot in *c* was the slope of the green line in *b* between the dashed gray lines).

The predicted WFRs from the first slice method are presented in Figure 3. For all calculations, scala height was taken to be 337.5 μ m (the height of ST—the smaller height of the two scalae), and the density was 1000 kg/m³. For the wavenumber calculation including viscosity, dynamic fluid viscosity was 7e-4 Pa s. The long-wave approximation was plotted for all frequencies but should only be considered below the transition frequency around 1000 Hz. Likewise, the short-wave and viscous approximations should be considered above the transition frequency. To twice the BF, the predicted WFR showed remarkable agreement deviating by a maximum of 1.5 times the true WFR from

FIGURE 3. Stationary study and predicted WFRs from first slice method using the calculations described in Puria and Steele, 2008 [6]. (a) Stationary study of partition deflection under 1 Pa pressure input on the SV face. (b) Predicted WFRs compared to full box WFR. The gray dashed line with markers indicates the WFR calculated from the velocity phase slope of the full box model, as seen in Fig. 1c. The light orange and orange lines were the calculated long and short-wave wavenumber approximations from Eqs. 3 and 4, respectively, while the dark red line was the 2D viscous approximation from Eq. 5. The best frequency was 1250 Hz.

the full box. The maximum deviation falls to 1.26 times when considering frequencies below 1.5 times the BF (1875 Hz) with that offset occurring near 500 Hz. While the calculated effect of viscosity was to increase the WFR relative to the short-wave approximation at high frequencies, we did not see this in the full box WFR. Rather, the full box wavenumber was lower than the short-wave approximation would suggest. The origins of this discrepancy at high frequencies are unknown but solid damping (i.e. a non-zero resistance in Z_{ooc} from Eqs. 9 and 10) could be a contributing factor.

The WFR calculated from the second slice method is presented in Fig. 4. The scala height and density were the same as in the first method. Since the approach required numerical iteration, the 0th, 1st, and 10th iterations were plotted with the 0th equivalent to k_{lw} from Fig. 3 and Eq. 3. By the 10th iteration, the wavenumber at frequencies well below the BF approached the long-wave approximation and at frequencies well above the BF approached the short-wave approximation.

FIGURE 4. Predicted WFRs from first slice method using the calculations described in Shera and Altoe, 2023 [7]. The gray dashed line with markers indicates the WFR calculated from the velocity phase slope of the full box model, as seen in Fig. 1c. The light green, green, and dark green lines are the wavenumber calculations from the 0th, 1st, and 10th iterations where the 0th iteration (k_0) is k_{lw} from Fig. 3 (i.e. $\alpha = 1$ for all frequencies).

Lastly, we predicted the WFR for the slice using calculations from de La Rochefoucauld and Olson, 2007. This impedance WFR calculation used values for scala height and density equivalent to those used in the previous two methods and included $\varepsilon = 0.3654$ (BM fractional width from the 7 mm location in the model) and $b_0 = 1.2$. These calculations were also iterative, and the results are shown in Figure 5. Solving the slice model in the frequency domain required boundary conditions on the longitudinal walls, so we began by assuming no knowledge of the WFR and prescribing the continuity condition. This condition required the fluid pressure and velocity in addition to solid displacements to match in magnitude and phase from one wall to the other. In effect, this made for an infinitely long wavelength or a wavenumber of zero, so $k_0 = 0$ for all frequencies. With the model solutions using the continuity condition, we calculated a frequency dependent impedance and new WFR (k_1). This WFR was roughly linear below

FIGURE 5. Predicted WFRs from third slice method using calculations outlined in de La Rochefoucauld and Olson, 2007 [8]. The gray dashed line with markers indicates the WFR calculated from the velocity phase slope of the full box model, as seen in

Fig. 1c. The light purple line indicates the wavenumber of the continuity boundary condition ($k_0 = 0$). The first through fifth iterations are plotted from light to dark blue. An average of the first four iterations is shown in purple.

the BF and quadratic above, which aligned with the stiffness-only approaches above. However, upon iteration, this relationship did not hold. Interestingly, the WFR was converging for stimulus frequencies below the BF and exhibited a flutter or oscillatory instability above the BF. The cause of these behaviors is unknown, but since our goal was to explore methods that predicted the WFR, we took an average across iterations to reasonably approximate the full box WFR beyond the BF. To 1.5 times the BF, an average of the first four iterations (k_{avg} , purple line in Fig. 5) stayed within a factor of 1.5 of the full box WFR.

In conclusion, the methods presented here allowed us to predict a traveling wave WFR from a slice model that closely matched the WFR found in the corresponding full-length model. Simulating the traveling wave in cochlear slice models is important for capturing the micromechanical features of full-length models while significantly reducing the computational cost associated with them, which increases dramatically with the inclusion of more microscopic morphological detail. These methods will allow us to generate physiologically appropriate WFRs for slice models of varying cochlear locations from base to apex in different species vastly expanding our knowledge of cochlear micromechanics.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Online Forum]

[Yi-Wen-Liu]: Nice comparison of two WFR computation methods. I am curious about whether these two methods can be extended to model the imaginary part of the WFR; i.e., when the stimulus frequency exceeds the characteristic frequency of the partition, I suppose that the wavenumber would become purely imaginary, indicating an evanescent mode. Could you add a discussion or direct us to some further readings?

I am also curious whether this method can apply to cochlear partition with active outer hair cells.

[Gabriel Alberts]: The wavenumber would not become purely imaginary but complex. While the methods can be extended to include the imaginary component of the wavenumber, this is not used for our purposes. With the real and imaginary components of the wavenumber, one can reconstruct the magnitude and phase. We are using the real part to solve a finite-element model, so we aim to allow the physics of the system to produce the magnitude response. The Puria and Steele book chapter includes information about this topic.

Additionally, we do hope to apply this method to a partition with active outer hair cells. We have shown in previous presentations that it is possible to get amplification in cochlear slice models, and Julius Kraut's poster this year expands on that work. I encourage you to visit his poster!

[Puria and Steele - 2008 - Mechano-Acoustical Transformations.pdf](#)

[Renata Sisto]: Dear Gabriel

I read with great interest your work! I would have some suggestions for you. In the 2D cochlear model, containing the full hydrodynamical coupling, I proposed to add the contribution of the viscous friction force at the interface between the BM and the fluid. This contribution can be inserted in the admittance as a damping term proportional to the wavenumber itself. The role of this term is that stabilizing the wavevector growth due to the focusing of the fluid.

You should use the short wave wavevector, the k proportional to the admittance, and iteratively correct the admittance with the viscous term depending on k .

The iterative procedure rapidly converges. The procedure is described in the JASA paper Sisto et al. 2021 Fluid focusing.....

And in the subsequent paper Sisto et al JASA 2023 Crucial factor....

Extending the 2D results to a 3D model.

As your full length model contains the full coupling between the structure and the fluid I think that, including the viscosity, would be successful in getting the right k .

You could also fit the best value for the viscosity parameter

Let me know if it works

If you needed any help, I would be happy to give it

Renata

[Poster Discussion]

Alessandro Altoe: The BM admittance is typically defined with a mass and damping term in addition to the stiffness term. The stiffness-only admittance works well in this case but might not translate for other frequency locations or models with additional structures.

[Gabriel Alberts]: The stiffness-only admittance was used to find agreement with the Puria and Steele approach. We will look into incorporating a more detailed admittance term, like the one Renata suggested, in a future version of this work.

POSTER BLITZ

At the Poster Blitz, the author (Gabriel Alberts) recited a poem to accompany his slides. The poem and visual references are reproduced below.

Mother Nature, Organ of Corti

She is beauty
She is grace
With each new tune
She dances in place

Credit: Prof. Andrew Forge

One step to the left
One to the right
One step up--
She dances all night

But what are
These moves she makes?
Let's take a slice
To investigate

Hair cells with hair bundles
On a basilar membrane
Such morphological detail
Captured in plane

Credit: Andrew Tubelli

Out of plane
I must confess
We need a wave
To make progress

And what type
Of wave is this?
What is the
Wavenumber-frequency relationship?

Credit: Hamid Motallebzadeh

How do we predict this wave
You may implore
See me at PS18
To learn more

